

Appendix A

Key concepts from the six corpora

	Key concepts from "Bibliography Old"	Score
1	research data management	94,9054
2	data conservancy instance	94,9054
3	data curation education program	94,9054
4	data curation education	88,5496
5	data curation profile	88,5496
6	data curation	77,3987
7	data management	77,3987
8	research data	77,3987
9	data preservation	77,3987
10	data sharing	77,3987
11	curation	57,1213
12	principle of data sharing	48,2296
13	courses in data	44,9066
14	digital curation	23,3742
15	research data curation	17,2466
16	data curation service	17,2466
17	practices for data policies	16,6488
18	coherent research data management organization	16,4768
19	practices in data	15,3900
20	data management plan	14,1511
21	roles of research libraries	12,7902
22	large scale information management problems	9,9581
23	curation across different research	9,9312
24	issue of curation	9,2867
25	preservation	9,1689
26	ec-funded digital curator vocational education	9,1412
27	management of scientific research	9,1255
28	digital preservation	7,7914
29	management of datasets	7,7389
30	research information network	6,7713
31	data quality	6,4928
32	data information literacy	6,1909
33	scientific data	6,1837
34	handling of data sets	6,1218
35	permanent research data curation program	5,6428
36	area of data	5,5512
37	plurality of curation roles	5,5030
38	skills of research libraries	5,4815
39	data management skills	5,3067
40	open access	5,2561
41	information management strategy	5,1595
42	different roles	5,0500

	Key concepts from “Bibliography Old”	Score
43	variety of science disciplines	5,0301
44	data librarian	4,7122
45	data management services	4,6433
46	implementation of interoperability guidelines	4,5572
47	digital curator vocational education	4,5190
48	curation activities	4,5041
49	scientific data specialists	4,4222
50	repositories	4,4163
51	curation researchers	4,2805
52	infrastructure	4,2156
53	curation professionals	4,1637
54	curation tools	4,0606
55	barriers information professionals	4,0326
56	information resources	4,0178
57	data stewardship	3,8957
58	escience professionals	3,6965
59	metadata	3,1115
60	research data management organization	2,7468

	Key concepts from “Bibliography New”	Score
1	research data management	98,2333
2	research data services	98,2333
3	data curation education	98,2333
4	data curation profiles toolkit	98,2333
5	big data	92,4521
6	data curation profiles	92,4521
7	data curation	74,9336
8	research data	74,7245
9	data management	74,7245
10	curation	55,5193
11	delivery of research data	50,4706
12	digital curation	22,3212
13	ongoing data life cycle management	18,3147
14	meaning among data curationstakeholders	17,8077
15	digital asset management	15,4488
16	data management planning	15,1679
17	academic libraries	13,6991
18	research data curation	11,3759
19	large scale information management problems	11,1183
20	big data curation academic	10,8951
21	management of scientific information	10,5001
22	pervasive curation practices	10,1661
23	plurality of curation roles	9,4719
24	data curation profiles directory	9,3238
25	central research information technologies unit	8,9353

	Key concepts from “Bibliography New”	Score
26	academic libraries collaboration research libraries	8,7873
27	electronic publication article	7,9603
28	researcher data management practices	7,7699
29	data quality	7,4402
30	science data	7,4402
31	research institutions	7,4402
32	effective research data curation services	7,3999
33	framework of research data	6,9201
34	data curation research	6,9148
35	digital preservation	6,6962
36	data literacy	6,6962
37	escience professionals	6,6962
38	role of information professionals	6,6229
39	different curation roles	6,6089
40	expertise in knowledge management	6,5181
41	data curation research data	6,3116
42	effective research data	6,2197
43	role in digital curation	6,2159
44	perceptions of data management	6,2159
45	preservation of research data	6,2159
46	preservation	6,1288
47	capacity of storage infrastructure	6,0309
48	data collection	5,9522
49	repositories	5,8369
50	digital library education	5,8184
51	big data curation	5,6880
52	data management support	5,6880
53	data curation center	5,6880
54	data curation network	5,6880
55	data science	5,3088
56	curation competencies	5,2081
57	library roles	4,9601
58	curation roles	4,9365
59	data ecosystem	4,8716
60	data skills	4,8681
61	curation practices	4,5735
62	information management	4,5350
63	curation services	4,4870
64	metadata practices	4,3696
65	digital repositories	4,2516
66	metadata	3,7768
67	reproducibility	3,2804
68	curators	2,7468
69	information professionals	2,6041

Key concepts from “Job offers”	Score
1 research data curation librarian	45,9738
2 research data management	37,8947
3 data management librarian	37,8947
4 research data curation	37,8947
5 data curation	32,7076
6 research data	27,2370
7 curation	24,6806
8 repositories for sharing data	23,3087
9 librarians on data	19,1844
10 data management	16,0284
11 digital preservation	11,2280
12 digital scholarship librarian	11,1635
13 skills in resource discovery	9,2108
14 research data service	7,8239
15 digital scholarship	7,3226
16 preservation	6,7275
17 collection management	6,6949
18 repository platforms ability	6,3852
19 digital life cycle management issues	6,3429
20 scholarly communication librarian	6,3429
21 curation of scholarly output	6,0046
22 communication skills	5,6954
23 familiarity with data management	5,1548
24 digital curation librarian	5,0743
25 metadata management system	5,0204
26 data management specialist	4,9789
27 curation in research	4,8129
28 digital library services	4,7945
29 training for libraries staff	4,6716
30 scholarly communication	4,4749
31 use of metadata standards	4,1883
32 high security standards	4,0424
33 data management planning	3,9831
34 data curation librarian	3,9831
35 security standards	3,9596
36 digital repositories archivist	3,9467
37 interdisciplinary science librarian	3,9265
38 university digital conservancy	3,8057
39 visual data curation	3,7341
40 digital curation	2,7663

Key concepts from “Questionnaire”	Score
1 research data management	125,6693
2 research data officer	96,7222
3 research data manager	96,7222

Key concepts from "Questionnaire"	Score
4 research data services	96,7222
5 research data facility manager	96,7222
6 research data management services	96,7222
7 research data facility	84,6894
8 research data	74,7087
9 data management	53,8040
10 subject expertise and data expertise	51,9434
11 progress of research data	51,1171
12 information management	38,3665
13 information security skills	27,4404
14 metadata standards	27,0733
15 curation	23,5877
16 knowledge in ipr issues	22,5685
17 life cycle management activities	22,1448
18 good research data management practices	19,8818
19 use of research data	18,9455
20 data curation	16,5524
21 knowledge of management workflows	12,4127
22 oais reference model	12,0735
23 knowledge of project management	12,0629
24 data stewardship	12,0365
25 research data management policies	12,0365
26 knowledge in data management	12,0365
27 data management planning	11,7585
28 digital preservation	11,6480
29 information management skills	11,4395
30 open access data archiving	11,4388
31 specific metadata standards data preservation	11,1051
32 data curator	10,4987
33 data sharing	10,3381
34 aspects of information security	10,2991
35 identification of stakeholders	9,4215
36 digital life cycle management	9,3834
37 maintenance of data quality	9,1707
38 definition of data curation	9,1707
39 technical tasks data curation teams	9,1349
40 range of research data	8,2216
41 project management skills	7,4826
42 allocation of resources	7,2091
43 data archive	6,9991
44 preservation	6,9376
45 research data lifecycle	6,8047
46 curation tasks	6,6484
47 publication practices	6,2371
48 archiving	5,9465
49 digital curation	5,8107

	Key concepts from “Questionnaire”	Score
50	data quality	5,7574
51	curator	5,6161
52	data manager	5,4832
53	preservation metadata	5,2090
54	master of information management	4,5853
55	publication workflow	4,4094
56	repositories	3,3036

	Key concepts from “Interviews”	Score
1	research data management	32,0633
2	data management	27,1857
3	research data	27,1857
4	data curation	27,1857
5	better research data management services	16,1450
6	understanding in research data	16,1162
7	research data specialist	15,3433
8	thing that researchers care	11,5760
9	data management plan	8,3373
10	better research data management practices	5,4572
11	bolts of research data	5,4296
12	focus on data	5,1575
13	publishing data	4,5738
14	curation	4,3660
15	research support services	4,0779
16	scholarly communication support researchers	3,9205
17	things like workflow analysis	3,0801
18	idea of data stewards	1,8674
19	area of data	1,7622
20	metadata	1,7379
21	experts in research management	1,5708
22	services for research	1,4023
23	digital curation	1,3957
24	faculty with metadata standards	1,3270
25	metadata production specialist	1,3159
26	areas of expertise	1,3127
27	role of research institutions	1,2730
28	kind of repository solution	0,9537
29	institutional repository managers	0,9469
30	data repository	0,9434
31	curators	0,9169
32	library information science	0,8780
33	scholarly communication	0,7654
34	current research information system	0,5891

	Key concepts from “Edison”	Score
1	data science	97,8236
2	data science data management	28,0304
3	data science taxonomy	22,5791
4	data science education	22,5791
5	data science knowledge	22,5791
6	advanced data mining tools	20,8210
7	data science competence	16,6358
8	data management	15,8576
9	data science model	14,7004
10	big data lifecycle management	11,1604
11	data intensive science	7,5664
12	data scientist	7,3434
13	data science profession	6,4855
14	advanced analytics tools	6,4512
15	data lifecycle management	6,2693
16	data science skills	5,6208
17	scientific data lifecycle management	5,5914
18	big data analytics	5,5590
19	business analysis	4,8630
20	curation	3,7406
21	data curation	3,3843
22	data science analytics	3,1347
23	data analysis	3,0876
24	lifecycle management	2,3258
25	data quality	2,2553